

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FACTORS OF THE FORMATION OF LEXICAL
COMPETENCE IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE OF A2 LEVEL
STUDENTS IN PRACTICAL LESSONS

Turg'unboyev Muhammadbobur Faxriddin o'g'li

Master student of Namangan state institute of foreign languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7797025>

Annotation

In this article, the author discusses in detail the psycholinguistic factors of the formation of lexical competence in English of A2 level students in practical lessons. Also summarizes the empirical research methods conducted by the author.

Key words: lexical competence, communicative competence, psycholinguistics, interlinguistic integration, foreign language

Аннотация

В данной статье автор подробно рассматривает психолингвистические факторы формирования лексической компетенции по английскому языку у студентов уровня А2 на практических занятиях. Также обобщаются эмпирические методы исследования, проведенные автором.

Ключевые слова: лексическая компетентность, коммуникативная компетентность, психолингвистика, межъязыковая интеграция, иностранный язык.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada muallif A2 darajadagi o'quvchilarning ingliz tilidagi leksik kompetensiyasini amaliy darslarda shakllantirishning psiholingvistik omillari atroflicha muhokama qilinadi. Hamda Muallif o'tkazgan imperik tadqiqot metodlarini xulosalaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: leksik kompetensiya, kommunikativ kompetensiya, psiholingvistika, tillararo integratsiya, xorijiy til

Introduction. The issue of the formation of foreign language communicative competence, in particular lexical competence (hereinafter referred to as LC), is considered in a number of works. For the most part, they represent a study of the process of formation of foreign-language LC in students, whereas the problem of formation of LC when learning a foreign language in primary school has been little studied. Lexical competence, being a part of linguistic competence, is a part of communicative competence. Therefore, its formation is one of the goals of teaching foreign languages, which is prescribed in the Federal State Educational Standard (FGOS) and the Approximate program of primary

general education [1]. "As practice shows, work on lexical material is often schematic, unsystematic in nature. The results of the cross-sections ... showed that the level of possession of lexical skills ... among students remains low [2].

Methods While the importance of the lexical aspect of learning a foreign language is undeniable. E.V. Yataeva emphasizes: "... vocabulary proficiency is an important indicator of the level of foreign language communicative competence" [3]. After all, it is precisely qualitatively formed lexical skills that determine the success of communication in a foreign language. However, the researcher clarifies that "at the same time, the lexical aspect is one of the most difficult aspects of the theory and practice of teaching a foreign language. The process of acquiring learners' lexical skills contains a complex of problems related to the multidimensional nature of a word that has a grammatical and proper (lexical) status, the multidimensionality of semantic relations of a word in a dictionary, the immediate the correlation of the word with non-linguistic reality" [4]. In foreign language classes, the main way of forming a linguistic picture of the world is language and especially vocabulary. And the basics of LC should be laid already at the initial stage of training. However, another problem is that there is no unambiguous interpretation of the concept of LC. Here are some examples: In the document "Pan-European competencies: study, teaching, evaluation", the following definition of LC is given: knowledge of the vocabulary of a language consisting of lexical and grammatical elements, as well as the ability to use it. A.A. Fetisova in her dissertation defines this concept as the ability and readiness of a student "on the basis of a set of acquired lexical knowledge, skills and skills, language and speech experience to carry out correct interpersonal and intercultural foreign language communication ... with linguistic, stylistic and socio-cultural norms of language" [5]. A.N. Shamov offers his definition of the concept of LC. He has this "the ability of a person to determine the contextual meaning of a word, compare the volume of its meaning.in two languages, determine the structure of the meaning of a word, determine the specifically national meaning of a word" [6, p. 186]. K.V. Alexandrov in his monograph "Multimedia complex in teaching foreign language vocabulary ..." suggests clarifying the definition lexical competence, given by A.N. Shamov, as follows: "...based on lexical knowledge, skills, abilities, as well as personal language and speech experience the ability of a person to determine the contextual meaning of a word, compare the scope of its meaning in two languages, understand the structure of the meaning of a word and highlight a specifically national meaning of the word" [1, p. 59]. With regard to primary school, we find the following

definition in the research of I.P. Korotkova: "... the concept of lexical competence ... is the ability to recognize lexical units in the oral and written text, to work with text material in accordance with the educational task, to operate with the studied vocabulary in the process of communication, to identify simple word-forming elements, to use a linguistic guess in a complex textual situation in the process of reading and listening (international and complex words), which makes it possible to ensure successful mastery of the basics of all types of speech activity".

Results For the formation of any phenomenon, especially one as complex as competence, a clear sequence of actions is necessary in order to obtain the most optimal, successful result. Especially in elementary school, when the lexical and grammatical base is laid on in a foreign language, it is important to competently build the process of formation and further development of lexical competence. According to A.N. Shamov, the formation of LC begins with the accumulation of empirical knowledge, that is, observations of the functioning of lexical units in different contexts. At this stage, the presentation and semanticization of new vocabulary is organized. In addition, students get acquainted with the communicative behavior that is typical for native speakers in the proposed communication situation.

Discussion The second level of development of students' lexical competence assumes the for- improving the skills of using the studied lexical units, establishing strong links between lexical units and their meaning. Thanks to the training of the studied vocabulary at this stage, primary skills of using words in a given communicative context are acquired. The third level of lexical competence development is associated with the acquisition of theoretical knowledge about the lexical system of the studied language. Of course, the amount of this knowledge for primary school is very limited. But even at this educational stage , there is a srt organization of work on the establishment by students of the features of the form, structure and meanings of the word, which contributes to the creation of stronger verbal and semantic connections. The final, fourth, level of development of lexical competence is associated with the development of younger schoolchildren's skills in using lexical units to solve various communicative tasks. This level of competence is associated with the performance of practical actions with a foreign word using the necessary language knowledge, speech skills and abilities [8]. The selection of language material should be carried out based on its communicative value, significance, correspondence to the life experience of children of this age and their

vocabulary in the native language. The material should be introduced in large blocks united by a common communicative function, belonging to the same communication situation, etc.

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize once again the importance of the LC and the need for its formation, starting from the first year of foreign language training.

References:

1. Egorov EG. Tests and studies of low voltage switching electrical apparatus. Cheboksary.: Chuvash. University, 2000.448 p.
2. Shtremberg TK, Belozerova NA, Gartmanova IS. Estimation of the contact resistance using gamma distribution. Questions of radio electronics. Wired communication technology. 1969;3:34-42.
3. Shevchenko VV, Gracheva EI. Determination of the resistance of contact connections of low voltage switching devices. Promyshlennaya energetika. 2002;1:42-43.
4. Herzbach IB, Kordonsky H.B. Failure Models. M : Soviet Radio, 1966. 165p.
5. Kolemaev VA, Kalinina VN. Theory of Probability and Mathematical Statistics. 2nd ed. M.: UNITY-DANA, 2003. 352 p.
6. Fedorov OV, Sarvarov A.S., Petushkov M.Yu. Electromagnetic compatibility of starting devices for AC electric drives with a power supply network. Scientific works of Vinnitsa National Technical University. 2015;4:18-21.
7. Gracheva EI, Safin AR, Sadykov RR. Application of an analytical method for calculating the reliability of elements of power supply systems based on probabilistic models. Reliability and Safety of Energy. 2017;1:48-52.
8. Gracheva EI, Sadykov RR. Formation of models for assessing the operational reliability of the systems of internal power supply. News of the higher educational institutions of the Black Earth Region. 2017;1(47):27-38.

